

DEVELOPMENT OF AN IMPROVED ALCOHOL (ETHANOL)-BASED HAND SANITIZER (ABHS) FORMULATION THROUGH THE INCORPORATION OF YLANG-YLANG ESSENTIAL OIL

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has prompted international, national, and local governments to take action to reduce the disease's impact on people. Several interventions were implemented to control and prevent the spread of COVID-19, including consistent personal hygiene and periodic disinfection. The use of hand sanitizer became popular and was discovered to be the most effective method of protection. The World Health Organization (WHO) has developed an alcohol-based hand sanitizer (ABHS) formulation that they have made available as guidelines for organizations interested in developing ABHSs. While suitable for antimicrobial topical use, the formulation's distinct chemical odor hinders effective hand hygiene practices. This study aimed to address the issue by incorporating ylang-ylang essential oil into the formulation, following a descriptive developmental research design. The study was carried out by creating ABHS from an initial formulation and testing its consumer acceptability and skin tolerability with validated survey questionnaires adapted from WHO. The survey results were benchmarked against WHO's ABHS acceptability and tolerability criteria, leading to necessary adjustments in the ABHS formulation until excellent acceptability was achieved. After two rounds of optimization, empirical data indicate that the ABHS formulation, which contained 70% ethyl alcohol (v/v) and 0.10% ylang-ylang essential oil (v/v), met WHO standards for acceptability and skin tolerability. This study developed a hand sanitizer with high

consumer acceptability and skin tolerance scores. The research-validated ABHS formulation may be commercialized, potentially boosting the local and national ylang-ylang economy.

Keywords: *Alcohol-Based Hand Sanitizer, Ylang – Ylang Essential Oil, Skin tolerability, Hand hygiene*

INTRODUCTION

The emergence and rapid spread of infectious diseases have consistently posed significant challenges to global public health. Recently, the world has experienced the profound impact of COVID-19, a novel coronavirus that led to a global pandemic, alongside the re-emergence of Monkeypox, a zoonotic virus with rising incidence in various regions. Despite differences in transmission modes and clinical manifestations, both diseases highlight the critical need for effective preventive measures to limit their spread. COVID-19 is primarily transmitted through respiratory droplets when an infected person sneezes, coughs, or speaks (Li et al., 2020). This communicable virus has caused widespread outbreaks, overwhelming healthcare systems, and resulting in acute illness and fatality worldwide (Wu et al., 2020). Similarly, monkeypox, while less contagious than COVID-19, spreads through direct contact with bodily fluids, skin lesions, or contaminated items (Reynolds et al. 2006). The recent reappearance of monkeypox has prompted concerns about potential epidemics, especially in places with poor access to healthcare and preventive measures (McCollum and Damon, 2014).

Hand hygiene is essential for infection prevention, and alcohol-based hand rubs provide an effective way to sanitize the skin. Alcohol-based hand rubs are one of the most effective and widely recommended ways to prevent the spread of infectious diseases. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO) both recommend using hand sanitizers containing at least 60% alcohol because they are highly effective at inactivating a variety of viruses, including SARS-CoV-2 and the Monkeypox virus (Gold et al., 2021; Kampf et al., 2020).

The World Health Organization (WHO) proposed an alcohol-based handrub formulation to aid agencies and small pharmaceutical companies (WHO, 2022). This formulation aligns with the recommendations of various health, food, and pharmaceutical organizations in the United States (US Food and Drug Administration [USFDA], 2021). However, its distinct chemical odor affects overall user preference. Adding certain essential oils can improve its scent and antimicrobial effectiveness. Ismail et al. (2019) found that incorporating *Syzygium aromaticum* and *Piper nigrum* essential oils enhanced the antibacterial properties of the WHO formulation. Similarly, Wijana et al. (2020) developed a handrub with orange peel essential oil, which consumers preferred for its sweet scent.

Ylang-ylang (*Cananga odorata*) essential oil is recognized for its antibacterial properties and appealing scent, making it an ideal component for hand sanitizers (Tan et al., 2015). Research has shown that ylang-ylang essential oil has antifungal and antibacterial effects against various pathogens, such as *Candida tropicalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Escherichia coli* (Elkenawy et al., 2023). Moreover, this essential oil has skin-soothing properties that can help alleviate the drying effects of alcohol, particularly ethanol (Orchard & Van Vuuren, 2017).

Adding ylang-ylang essential oil to alcohol-based hand sanitizers can increase antibacterial efficacy by improving the germ-killing mechanism. Furthermore, it improves the sanitizer's sensory properties, such as smell and skin feel, making it more appealing to users and possibly increasing hand hygiene compliance (Orchard & Van Vuuren, 2017). Furthermore, ylang-ylang essential oil can help to reduce the drying and irritating effects of frequent alcohol-based sanitizer use, promoting overall skin health (Tan, 2015).

This study establishes the groundwork for a more thorough evaluation into the possible benefits of adding ylang-ylang essential oil to alcohol-based hand sanitizers. The researchers hope to design a more effective and user-preferred hand hygiene product that will lead to better public health outcomes by evaluating its acceptance and skin tolerability.

Research Questions

This study seeks to improve the formulation of an ethanol-based hand sanitizer by incorporating Ylang-ylang essential oil. The paper aims to address the following inquiries:

1. What is the optimal concentration of the ABHS primary components, specifically ethanol, glycerol, and ylang-ylang essential oil?
2. How well does the optimal ABHS formulation perform in terms of skin tolerability and user acceptability assessment score, as determined by World Health Organization (WHO) criteria?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive developmental research design, with participants evaluating an initial ABHS formulation and using the findings as a foundation for formulation development. The study was conducted at Tarlac State University's Villa Lucinda Extension Campus in Binauganan, Tarlac City. The study was conducted locally to ensure proper monitoring of survey participants as well as their proximity to the "observer". At least forty (40) survey respondents were asked to participate in the evaluation process. Those who agreed to participate in the product evaluation had to sign an informed consent form. All participant information remained strictly confidential.

Product Preparation

Ethyl alcohol ($\geq 95\%$), glycerol ($\geq 99\%$), hydrogen peroxide (3%), and pure Ylang-ylang (*Cananga odorata*) Essential Oil (pure) were procured and purchased through the procurement office of the Tarlac State University. All chemicals were of at least technical grade and came with a safety data sheet to ensure accurate assay and safeness of the chemicals.

The ethanol concentration in raw material (RM) was determined using a calibrated alcoholmeter. Exact amounts of the RM were calculated following the recommended percentage based on the measured concentration of the ethyl alcohol raw material summarized in Table 1 using the formula written below (United States Pharmacopeia [USP], 2021):

$$\text{volume of starting RM required} = \frac{(\text{final \% RM}) \times (\text{final volume of preparation})}{(\text{starting \% RM})}$$

Table 1: Percentage (v/v) of raw material in the alcohol-based hand sanitizer final product.

Chemical Raw Material	Percentage (v/v)
Ethanol (96%)	78.125 % (WHO, 2022)
Glycerol	1.45% (WHO, 2022) (initially), <i>succeeding % will depend on developed formulation</i>
Hydrogen Peroxide (3%)	4.17% (WHO, 2022)
Essential Oil (Ylang-ylang)	variable
Distilled Water	variable

Eight (8) liters of alcohol-based hand sanitizer were prepared according initially to the WHO's guidelines (WHO, 2022), with minor modifications with the addition of Ylang-ylang essential oil. The final product contained the following formulation:

Table 2: Percentage (v/v) content in the alcohol-based hand sanitizer final product.

Content	Percentage (v/v)
Ethanol	75 (± 2.0) %
Glycerol	1.45 (initially), <i>succeeding % will depend on developed formulation</i>
Hydrogen Peroxide	0.125%
Essential Oil (Ylang-ylang)	variable
Distilled Water	variable

ABHS Tolerability and Acceptability Assessment

Participants were required to meet with the “observer” before using the ABHS. The “observer” assessed the participants’ initial hand skin condition using the WHO assessment tool (Larson et al., 1986; Larson et al., 1997; USP, 2021; WHO, 2021), with minor modifications tailored to the study’s objectives. This represented their hands’ pre-use state and will be used in future comparisons.

Participants were given 200mL of ABHS in standardized spray bottles and told to use it exclusively as an “alcohol-based hand sanitizer” for seven (7) consecutive days, but they were not discouraged from washing their hands with soap and water during the testing period (Menegueti et al., 2019). Their personal needs determined how frequently they used ABHS.

The participants were instructed to meet with the “observer” again after seven (7) days of using the ABHS product. The “observer” used the assessment tool (Larson et al., 1986; Larson et al., 1997; USP, 2021; WHO, 2021) to rate the final condition of the survey respondents’ hand skin. This represented their hands’ post-use state, which was used for comparisons.

Participants were also given a subjective assessment tool based on the WHO-created and developed self-assessment survey, and they submitted their self-evaluation of the ABHS test product as well as their self-evaluation of the state of their hands after using the ABHS test.

Data Analysis

The survey results were organized and summarized using spreadsheets. A statistician used the general weighted average and standard deviation tool to analyze the pre- and post-use observer ratings, as well as participant evaluations, using the following rubrics:

Table 3: Rubrics used for the analysis of survey data.

Mean Interval	Verbal Description	Interpretation
5.00 - 7.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very Positive Response
3.00 - 4.99	Neutral (N)	Mixed Response
1.00 - 2.99	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Negative Response

Furthermore, product acceptability and skin tolerability were determined by the following criteria:

Product Acceptability Criteria (WHO, 2021):

- To pass the product evaluation criteria for the Smell parameter, more than 50% of participants must rate it above 4.
- To pass the product evaluation criteria for the other parameters, more than 75% of

participants must rate it above 4.

Criteria for skin tolerability (WHO, 2021):

- To pass the skin tolerability criteria for all parameters, more than 75% of participants must rate it above 4.
- To pass the evaluation of the state of skin criteria for all parameters, more than 75% of participants must be rated as 2 or lower by the “observer”.

If the ABHS product meets all the above requirements, the ABHS formulation selected will be the optimal alcohol-based hand sanitizer formulation. If the ABHS formulation failed the assessment based on statistical data analyses, it was modified. The new ABHS formulation was developed in the same way as the previous one; it will be packaged, distributed to participants, and evaluated in the same manner. The cycle was repeated until the product met the acceptability and skin tolerability criteria.

RESULTS

First Formulation Survey

Table 4 summarizes the concentrations of the raw materials used in the first batch of ABHS products.

Table 4: Percentage (v/v) content in the alcohol-based hand sanitizer final product (First Batch).

Content	Percentage (v/v)
Ethanol	75 (± 2.0)%
Glycerol	1.45%
Hydrogen Peroxide	0.125%
Essential Oil (Ylang-ylang)	0.50%
Distilled Water	diluent

The ABHS products were given to a total of 40 survey participants, who used them as their only hand sanitizer for seven (7) days. The survey results are summarized in Table 5, 6, and 7.

Table 5: Summary of Results for the Evaluation of the Test Product (First Batch)

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	STD DEV	MEAN	RESULT	% OF ABOVE 4 RATINGS
	SD	D	SwD	N	SwA	A	SA				
Smell	13	2	4	4	2	11	4	3.23	3.73	N	42.5%
Texture	0	0	1	2	2	1	34	1.19	6.63	SA	92.5%
Irritation	0	2	1	6	5	1	25	1.55	5.93	SA	77.5%
Drying Effect	0	2	2	6	1	0	29	1.64	6.05	SA	75.0%
Ease of Use	0	0	0	1	1	0	38	1.09	6.88	SA	97.5%

Speed of Drying	0	0	0	3	0	1	36	1.14	6.75	SA	92.5%
Application	2	0	0	6	5	4	23	1.61	5.90	SA	80.0%
Overall									5.98	SA	
Legend for Evaluation: <i>SD=Strongly Disagree; D=Disagree; SwD=Somewhat Disagree; N=Neither Agree Nor Disagree; SwA=Somewhat Agree; A=Agree; SA=Strongly Agree</i>											
Legend for Results: <i>SA=Strongly Agree (Very Positive Response); N=Neutral (Mixed Response); SD: Strongly Disagree (Very Negative Response)</i>											

The ABHS product must be rated above 4 by more than 50% of participants for the smell parameter and above 4 by more than 75% of participants for the other metrics in the “Evaluation of the Test Product” section to be considered acceptable (WHO, 2021). The product met the criteria for texture, irritation, ease of use, speed of drying, and application parameters. However, only 42.5% of participants rated the product as above 4 in terms of smell, while 75% rated it as above 4 in terms of irritation and drying effect.

The evaluation of the ABHS with Ylang-ylang essential oil produced positive findings across various metrics, except for the smell parameter. Participants in the study uniformly responded “strongly agree” to the ABHS’s effectiveness in sanitizing their hands. However, the “neutral” result for the smell criterion indicates that the strength of the scent provided by the ylang-ylang essential oil is not for everyone, which must be addressed to improve consumer acceptance of the product.

Table 6: Summary of Results for the Self-evaluation of state of skin on hands (First Batch)

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	STD DEV	MEAN	RESULT	% OF ABOVE 4 RATINGS
	SD	D	SwD	N	SwA	A	SA				
Appearance	0	0	1	7	5	5	22	1.29	6.00	SA	80.0%
Intactness	0	0	2	8	1	1	28	1.44	6.13	SA	75.0%
Moisture	0	0	5	9	3	1	22	1.63	5.65	SA	65.0%
Sensation	0	1	1	11	2	3	22	1.53	5.78	SA	67.5%
Overall									5.89	SA	
<i>*The legends are summarized in Table 5.</i>											

The ABHS product must be rated above 4 by more than 75% of participants for all the metrics in the “Self-evaluation of state of skin on hands” test to pass the skin tolerability test (WHO, 2021). According to the survey results, 80% of the participants gave an above-four rating for the appearance of the state of their hands’ skin, indicating that the appearance of their hands’ skin did not change significantly after using the product for 7 days. However, only 75% gave it a rating of 4 or higher in the intactness parameter, 65% in the moisture parameter, and 67.5% in the sensation parameter. Except for appearance, all parameters in this section of the survey received a rating of four or higher from at most 75% of participants, indicating that it fails the skin tolerability criteria.

All the parameters received a “strongly agree” average rating, indicating that the survey results had reached consensus.

Table 7: Summary of Results for the evaluation of skin condition by the observer (First Batch).

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	STD DEV	MEAN	RESULT	% OF BELOW 2 RATINGS
	SD	D	SwD	SwA	A	SA				
Redness	24	4	10	2	0	0	1.02	1.75	SD	70%
Scaliness	30	2	8	0	0	0	0.83	1.45	SD	80%
Fissures	34	0	6	0	0	0	0.78	1.30	SD	85%
Visual	24	0	14	0	2	0	1.23	1.90	SD	60%
Overall								1.60	SD	

**The legends are summarized in Table 5.*

Finally, to pass the skin tolerability test, more than 75% of the survey respondents’ hand-skin must receive a rating of 2 and below from the “observer” for all metrics in the “evaluation of skin condition by the observer” section. The initial batch of ABHS products met the scaliness and fissure parameter requirements. However, only 70% of the participants received a rating of less than 2 for the Redness parameter, and only 60% for the Visual parameter.

The major constituents of an alcohol-based hand sanitizer (ABHS), specifically ethanol, glycerol, and essential oils, determine its formulation and efficacy. Each of these components contributes significantly to the product’s overall effectivity and user acceptability.

The smell of the ABHS is directly related to the amount of ylang-ylang essential oil it contains. While this essential oil has antibacterial properties and a pleasant scent, higher concentrations can be overwhelming and unpleasant for some people. Initially, the formulation contained 0.50% (v/v) ylang-ylang essential oil, but the relatively strong scent received mixed feedback. To address this, the concentration was reduced to 0.10% in the new formulation, slightly reducing the strength of the ylang-ylang scent while maintaining its beneficial properties.

The concentrations of ethanol and glycerol in the ABHS have a significant impact on the skin’s appearance, integrity, moisture, and overall feel. Glycerol acts as a humectant, retaining moisture and preventing dryness, and ethanol is the primary antimicrobial agent (Meneguetti et al., 2019). The initial formulation struck a good balance between these components, resulting in positive feedback from users regarding its effects on their skin. Given the success of the initial glycerol concentration, it was kept in the new formulation to ensure continued skin hydration and user satisfaction.

The initial ABHS formulation met the criteria for quick drying, fissure prevention, and minimal scaliness, indicating a well-balanced product that dries quickly but leaves no

residue to cause skin fissures or scaliness. Maintaining the glycerol concentration was critical for retaining these beneficial properties in the updated formulation. Glycerol's moisturizing properties counteract ethanol's drying effects, ensuring the sanitizer is gentle on the skin.

The concentration of ethanol is critical not only for the sanitizer's effectiveness but also for its effect on the skin. High levels of ethanol can cause irritation, dryness, and redness (de Haan et al., 1996; Rotter, 1984). To address concerns raised during the initial survey, the ethanol concentration in the initial formulation was reduced from 75%(v/v) to 70%(v/v) in the following batch. This change is intended to maintain antimicrobial activity while improving skin tolerance and reducing irritation, making the sanitizer more suitable for daily use.

The initial ABHS formulation was modified to address concerns raised by the initial survey. The concentration of ylang-ylang essential oil was reduced from 0.5% to 0.1%, while the ethanol concentration decreased from 75% to 70%. The adjustments were intended to improve the product's odor acceptability and reduce potential skin irritation while maintaining antimicrobial effectiveness and moisturizing properties. The glycerol concentration remained constant, maintaining beneficial effects on skin hydration and overall user comfort.

Second Formulation Survey

The second formulation of the alcohol-based hand sanitizer (ABHS) was evaluated using several critical parameters indicated in the World Health Organization's (WHO, 2021) standards for user acceptability and skin health. Table 8 summarizes the concentrations of the raw materials used in the second batch of ABHS products.

Table 8: Percentage (v/v) content in the alcohol-based hand sanitizer final product (2nd Batch)

Content	Percentage (v/v)
Ethanol	70 (\pm 2.0) %
Glycerol	1.45%
Hydrogen Peroxide	0.125%
Essential Oil (Ylang-ylang)	0.10%
Distilled Water	diluent

The ABHS products were given to a total of 40 survey participants (the same as the first batch), who used them as their only hand sanitizer for seven (7) days. The survey results are summarized in Tables 9, 10, and 11.

Table 9: Summary of Results for the Evaluation of the Test Product (2nd Batch)

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	STD DEV	MEAN	RESULT	% OF ABOVE 4 RATINGS
	SD	D	SwD	N	SwA	A	SA				
Smell	1	4	5	6	10	10	4	1.97	4.65	N	60.0%
Texture	0	0	2	6	9	11	12	1.22	5.63	SA	80.0%
Irritation	1	2	1	4	5	8	19	1.63	5.75	SA	80.0%
Drying Effect	0	1	2	0	10	10	17	1.26	5.93	SA	92.5%
Ease of Use	0	0	0	0	6	8	26	1.04	6.50	SA	100.0%
Speed of Drying	0	0	0	5	5	15	15	1.04	6.00	SA	87.5%
Application	0	0	0	2	8	16	14	0.92	6.05	SA	95.0%
Overall									5.79	SA	

**The legends are summarized in Table 5.*

For the ABHS product to be deemed acceptable in terms of smell, more than half of the participants needed to rate it above 4. In the second batch evaluation, 60% of subjects rated the smell parameter as 5 or higher. This positive feedback indicates that the adjustment of the ylang-ylang essential oil concentration was successful, resulting in a pleasant and well-received scent among most users. This rating meets the acceptance threshold, demonstrating the product's success in this parameter.

For the ABHS product to be considered acceptable, more than 75% of participants needed to rate it four or higher for texture, irritation, drying effect, ease of use, drying speed, and application metrics. In the second batch evaluation, over 80% of participants rated these criteria as 5 or higher. These high ratings highlight the product's overall effectiveness and user satisfaction. The ideal ratio of ethanol to glycerol ensured a pleasant texture, minimized irritation, and provided a quick drying yet moisturizing experience.

The data from all parameters, except for the smell, received a "strongly agree" mean result, indicating uniform responses across the survey. However, the smell parameter received a "neutral" mean result, likely due to the subjective nature of scent preferences. Despite this, the second formulation passed all parameters.

Table 10: Summary of Results for the Self-evaluation of state of skin on hands (2nd Batch)

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	STD DEV	MEAN	RESULT	% OF ABOVE 4 RATINGS
	SD	D	SwD	N	SwA	A	SA				
Appearance	0	0	0	0	3	7	30	0.62	6.68	SA	100%
Intactness	0	0	0	0	3	8	29	0.62	6.65	SA	100%
Moisture	0	0	0	1	1	14	24	0.68	6.53	SA	97.5%
Sensation	0	0	0	0	3	12	25	0.64	6.55	SA	100%
Overall									6.60	SA	

**The legends are summarized in Table 5.*

To pass the self-evaluation section, more than 75% of participants had to rate the appearance, intactness, moisture, and sensation parameters as at least 4. Interestingly, more than 97% of participants rated these parameters as 5 or higher. This majority focuses on ABHS's excellent skin tolerability and moisturizing properties. The glycerol content most likely played an important role in keeping skin hydrated and intact, while the lower ethanol concentration reduced potential dryness and irritation. These findings show that the ABHS formulation effectively promotes skin health while meeting and exceeding the strict acceptability criteria.

All parameters received an average rating of "strongly agree," signifying consensus in the survey results.

Table 11: Summary of Results for the evaluation of skin condition by the observer (2nd Batch)

Parameter	1	2	3	4	5	6	STD DEV	MEAN	RESULT	% OF BELOW 2 RATINGS
	SD	D	SwD	SwA	A	SA				
Redness	40	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	1.00	SD	100%
Scaliness	38	2	0	0	0	0	0.22	1.05	SD	100%
Fissures	40	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	1.00	SD	100%
Visual	38	0	2	0	0	0	0.45	1.10	SD	95%
Overall								1.04	SD	

**The legends are summarized in Table 5.*

For the observer-based evaluation, more than 75% survey respondents' post-use hand skin needed to be rated as 2 or lower by the "observer" for redness, scaliness, fissures, and overall visual skin condition. After seven (7) days of using the second batch of ABHS, at least 95% of participants received ratings of two or one for these parameters. This finding suggests that the product did not cause significant skin issues, such as redness, scaliness, or fissures, in almost all users. The visual assessments confirmed that 95% of participants had no visible skin irritation or scaling, demonstrating the formulation's gentle nature and suitability for frequent use.

All parameters received an average rating of "strongly disagree," indicating consensus in the survey results.

DISCUSSION

Poor hand hygiene can cause significant skin damage, especially considering how much we rely on our hands daily. Amid the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and the resurgence of monkeypox, a well-formulated hand sanitizer is crucial. An effective hand sanitizer should be user-preferred, antibacterial, and gentle on the skin. The developed alcohol-

based hand sanitizer (ABHS) formulation achieves this by precisely balancing ethanol, glycerol, and ylang-ylang essential oil.

The primary active component of the ABHS is ethanol. Higher concentrations enhance antimicrobial efficacy but also increase the risk of skin irritation, dryness, and redness (de Haan et al., 1996; Rotter, 1984). Therefore, the final formulation contains 70% (v/v) ethanol. This concentration aligns with Sauerbrei's (2020) findings, which indicated that a safe bactericidal effect of ethanol occurs at concentrations between 60% and 85% (v/v). This is also consistent with Morakot et al. (1988), who observed that a 70% (v/v) ethanol concentration is effective against coronaviruses (but not parvoviruses). This concentration provides effective antimicrobial action while minimizing potential skin side effects, as demonstrated by high consumer acceptance and skin tolerance ratings.

Glycerol is used in the ABHS as a humectant and emollient to protect the skin from dryness and dermatitis, which can develop after repeated use. While glycerol is primarily used to moisturize, excessive amounts may inhibit ethanol's antibacterial activity (Suchomel et al., 2013; Suchomel et al., 2017). The final formulation contains 1.45% (v/v) glycerol, which effectively balances moisturizing benefits with the sanitizer's antimicrobial effectiveness. This glycerol concentration is in line with WHO recommendations, as evidenced by high ratings in parameters such as drying effect, drying speed, moisture, and skin integrity (Guidelines Review Committee [GRC], 2009). Furthermore, Meneguetti et al. (2019) discovered that this glycerol concentration was the second most effective concentration for an ethanol-based hand rub for people living in tropical climates, while Ismael et al. (2019) discovered that this glycerol concentration is practical because slightly increasing its concentration has no effect on microbial activity when combined with isopropanol.

Ylang-ylang essential oil is used in the ABHS primarily for its pleasant fragrance and antimicrobial properties (Ismail et al., 2019; Tan et al., 2015). However, excessive amounts can cause skin irritation due to the presence of the allergen dihydroisoeugenol (Toyoda et al., 1989). The final formulation contains 0.10% (v/v) Ylang-ylang essential oil, which provides a pleasant scent without having negative effects on the skin. This balance contributed to the study's strong evaluations for customer acceptance and skin tolerance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is therefore concluded that:

- For an alcohol-based hand sanitizer (ABHS), the optimal concentrations are 70% (v/v) ethyl alcohol, 1.45% (v/v) glycerol, and 0.10% (v/v) ylang-ylang essential oil. This combination results in a highly effective, well-tolerated, and user-friendly ABHS product.
- Ethanol has effective antimicrobial properties, glycerol keeps skin moisture and integrity, and Ylang-ylang essential oil improves the product's sensory acceptability while also contributing to its antimicrobial activity. The final ABHS formulation met all the WHO's skin tolerability and user acceptability assessment criteria, indicating that the product is an appealing, effective, and skin-friendly hand

sanitizer, making it an important tool for promoting hand hygiene.

Recommendations

1. Investigate other naturally occurring, sweet-smelling essential oils with antimicrobial properties as alternatives to ylang-ylang.
2. Expand the survey to include a larger, more diverse participant pool to better assess the formulation's efficacy across different skin types.
3. Explore the possibility of replacing glycerol with a naturally occurring essential oil that functions as a humectant in future research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was funded by Tarlac State University's Office of University Research Development. The authors declare no conflict of interest. The study did not involve any animal participants. Prior to the conduct of the study, the protocol was submitted for ethical clearance from Tarlac State University's Research Ethics Review Committee. All procedures involving human participants adhered to international ethical standards. Raw data were collected using validated survey forms, and each participant provided informed consent. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, findings were interpreted objectively, and results were used solely for research purposes. All chemicals used in this study were sourced from reputable suppliers through TSU's procurement office. Chemical waste generated during the study was collected in appropriate containers and delivered to TSU's Pollution Control and Safety Unit (PCSU) for safe and legal disposal.

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